

Interaction of *m*-Xylohydroquinone with D-Glucose, D-Galactose, and Chorionic Gonadotropin: A Chromatographic Study

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A chromatographic method of separation of the complex, formed by the interaction of *m*-xylohydroquinone with D-glucose, D-galactose, and chorionic gonadotropin, has been presented. In all these cases *m*-xylohydroquinone has been observed to move at the same rate with the complex formed from the spectrophotometric study after eluting the spots at the position of *m*-xylohydroquinone. Eluate furnishes two peaks, one at 260 $m\mu$ and the other at 290 $m\mu$. The former is attributed to the complex and the latter to *m*-xylohydroquinone.

In a previous spectrophotometric study¹, it was observed that pure D-galactose did not yield any absorption peak between 220 and 305 $m\mu$ and pure *m*-xylohydroquinone yielded an absorption peak at 290 $m\mu$. But when this hydroquinone was mixed with D-galactose, the peak at 290 $m\mu$ gradually disappeared with time and a new peak was observed at 260 $m\mu$. When sufficient galactose was used, the whole peak of the hydroquinone (at 290 $m\mu$) disappeared along with the appearance of a significant peak of sufficient height at 260 $m\mu$. This suggests a likely reaction of the sugar with the hydroquinone with the formation of a complex or loose chemical compound, absorption peak of which is at 260 $m\mu$. The complex was, however, found to be sufficiently stable to more than 48 hours of mixing, beyond which it gradually broke down into its constituents, as was evidenced by the disappearance of the peak at 260 $m\mu$ and the reappearance of that at 290 $m\mu$.

After this observation attempts have been made to isolate and characterise this complex by employing the chromatographic method and the results recorded in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Different solvents, including water, were used for ascertaining their optimum performance. All the solvents were mostly of the G. R. or A. R. quality or else purified by distillation once or twice under proper conditions. Mixtures of two or more solvents were also tried.

A mixture of D-galactose ($10^{-2}M$) and *m*-xylohydroquinone ($10^{-3}M$) was prepared in oxygen-free water. At first water was used as the solvent. Spots of this mixture of sugar and *m*-xylohydroquinone were put at different positions of the chromatographic filter paper (Whatman size I) and the paper was hung for 4 hr. in a chromatographic chamber, the interior of which was maintained saturated with water vapour. The water was allowed to run for 6 hr. and then the paper was dried and viewed in the UV light ($\lambda, 253.7 m\mu$). A few diffuse violet spots could be observed here and there. Although three spots corres-

ponding to the sugar, *m*-xylohydroquinone, and the complex were expected, only two, corresponding to the sugar and to the hydroquinone, could be identified.

Since the separation of the two spots was not satisfactory, other solvent mixtures were tried, viz., butanol-pyridine-benzene (5:3:1), chloroform-acetic acid-butanol (1:1:2), butanol-ethanol-water (1:1:2); of these, the last solvent mixture afforded a satisfactory separation of the spots, which again were apparently two in number.

To examine these spots further, the experiment was repeated several times; in one of them the spots were separated and isolated from each other by punching. The spots were then eluted with water and the eluate was examined within the range of 220 to 305 $m\mu$. The spot corresponding to *D*-galactose, as evidenced by a blank experiment, did not show any peak within this range. This suggests that the spot corresponds to galactose alone. The second spot, which coincided with that of *m*-xylohydroquinone, was also eluted with water and the eluate examined in the spectrophotometer. The absorption curve showed two peaks, one at 260 $m\mu$ and the other (a low one) at 290 $m\mu$ (Fig. 1, curve 1). The former is known to be produced by the complex and the latter by *m*-xylohydroquinone alone. So this second spot appeared to be due to a mixture of *m*-xylohydroquinone and the complex, which resisted separation from each other. The third spot for the complex, which was looked for, did not therefore separate itself from the hydroquinone in this way.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Experiments were then performed with chorionic gonadotropin and serum gonadotropin (hormones) solutions, each being mixed with *m*-xylohydroquinone. Absorption study of the eluate of one of the two spots shows two peaks, one corresponding probably to the hormone (at 260 $m\mu$)³ and the other to *m*-xylohydroquinone (at 290 $m\mu$) as in Fig. 1, curve 2. The other spot, which showed no absorption peak within the wave length range studied, was due to the chorionic gonadotropin (Fig. 1, curve 2). Serum gonadotropin behaved similarly to the chorionic gonadotropin (not shown in the figure).

2. Sanyal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1964, **41**, 627.

3. Sanyal and Ganguly, *Science & Culture*, 1954, **19**, 356.

In another set of experiments a mixture of D-glucose ($10^{-2}M$) and *m*-xylohydroquinone ($10^{-3}M$) was subjected to the same chromatographic procedure and the two spots obtained were later eluted with water and were spectrophotometrically examined for their absorption after 24 hours' run. Results are shown in curve 1, Fig. 2. The same experiment was repeated with the same substance under similar conditions, but the time allowed for mixing was 2 hr. only and the run was continued for 4 hr. so as to avoid decomposition of the complex formed on longer keeping. The two spots were then eluted with water and examined for absorption in UV (220 to 305 $m\mu$). Results appear in Fig. 2, curve 2.

TABLE I
Pure components.
(D-Galactose and *m*-xylohydroquinone)

Distance travelled by Solvent.	Distance travelled by Sugar.	R_f of sugar.	Distance travelled by Solvent.	Distance travelled by <i>m</i> -XHq.	R_f for <i>m</i> -XHq.
33.7 cm	23.8 cm	0.71	33.0 cm	31.0 cm	0.94
33.5	23.8	0.71	32.7	31.0	0.95
33.4	23.5	0.70	32.5	30.8	0.93
33.2	23.3	0.70	32.1	30.0	0.95
			31.7	30.0	

N.B. *m*-XHq denotes *m*-xylohydroquinone.

TABLE II
Mixture of D-galactose and m-xylohydroquinone.

Distance travelled by Solvent.	Distance travelled by 1st spot.	R_f .	Distance travelled by 2nd spot.	R_f .
32.3 cm	23.8 cm	0.71	32.2 cm	0.94
32.4	32.8	0.71	30.4	0.94
32.5	23.5	0.70	30.6	0.94
32.5	23.3	0.70	30.6	0.94

TABLE III
Mixture of chorionic gonadotropin and m-xylohydroquinone.

Distance travelled by Solvent.	Distance travelled by 1st spot.	R_f .	Distance travelled by 2nd spot.	R_f .
33.7 cm	21.4 cm	0.68	30.0 cm	0.96
31.5	21.6	0.68	30.0	0.95
31.2	21.3	0.68	29.7	0.95
34.0	23.1	0.68	32.5	0.96
			32.5	0.96

DISCUSSION

Spots are observed when mixtures of *m*-xylohydroquinone with D-galactose and with chorionic gonadotropin are subjected to paper chromatography. One of these corresponds to the pure sugar or pure hormone and the other to the complex formed as well as *m*-xylohydroquinone, but appearing at the same place as *m*-xylohydroquinone itself. This suggests that the complex and *m*-xylohydroquinone have got the same R_f value (Table I). That the second spot contains both the complex and the hydroquinone is evident from the peaks at 260 $m\mu$ and 290 $m\mu$, the former due to the complex¹ and the latter to *m*-xylohydroquinone¹.

A mixture of D-glucose and *m*-xylohydroquinone, when examined immediately, showed only one absorption maximum at 290 $m\mu$; but when the mixture was allowed to stand for about 2 hr. and then run in the chromatographic paper for 4 hr., the absorption curve tended to form a small peak at 260 $m\mu$, which disappeared on longer standing. A similar observation, recorded earlier², reveals that the complex so formed is short-lived.

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